

into races and six serological groups on the basis of their reactivity to a panel of six monoclonal antibodies (mAbs). We retested with a high-titer clone of mAb *Xco-1* and found that the strains of serogroups V and VII (which did not react earlier) gave very weak to moderate

Table 1. Serological classification of 87 Indian strains of *Xoo* with monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) and reactions with *Xoor* and T mAbs.

mAb	Serological group of <i>Xoo</i>			<i>Xoor</i>
	I	II	V	
<i>X1</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Xco-1</i>	+	+	-	-
<i>Xco-2</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Xco-5</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Xco-T</i> (225)	-	-	+ ^a	+
<i>Xco-T</i> (226)	-	-	+	-
<i>Xccola</i>	-	-	-	+
Strains (no.)	67	18	2 ^b	8

^a*Xoo* strain PXO86 (serogroup I) and USA strain X1-5 (serogroup III) showed positive reactions with the mAb.

^bT strains (T1, T2).

Table 2. Phenotypic characteristics of *Xoo*, *Xoor*, and weakly virulent bacterial strains from rice in India.

Phenotypic characteristic (17 strains)	<i>Xoo</i> (8 strains)	<i>Xoor</i> (8 strains)	T1, T2
Acetoin production	-	-	-
Growth on L-alanine	- ^a	+	+
Growth in presence of cupric nitrate (0.001%)	-	-	+
Growth on vitamin-free casamino-acid (0.2%)	- ^a	+	+
β-glucosidase production	+	+	+
Phenylalanine deaminase production	- ^a	+	-
Tyrosinase production	- ^a	-	+

^aStrain X1-5, a strain from Texas, USA, of a low-virulent *Xoo* was an exception.

enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay values (OD = 0.05 to 0.4) with *Sco-1* and therefore became part of serogroups I and II, respectively. Only two of the 70 strains did not react to *Xco-1*. A mAb-designated *Xco-T* was made to target them. This study reports on these T strains, T1 and T2, which have been characterized through plant inoculations, tests for phenotypic characteristics, and mAb and DNA probes.

Following inoculations, the T strains showed very low virulence to rice and did not cause BB symptoms on any of the differential rice cultivars after clip-inoculation. However, on swab-inoculation, we observed mild BB on IR8 and occasional streaks on DV85. Strains were re-isolated from these mild BB and BLS symptoms 14 d after inoculation.

T strains react with a genus-specific mAb for *Xanthomonas* and share some surface antigens with strains of *Xoo* and *X. o. pv. oryzicola* (*Xoor*) (BLS pathogen) (Table 1). The mAb clone 225.66.2.1, generated to a T strain, reacted with *Xoo* strains PXO86 and X1-5 and eight strains of *Xoor*. Likewise, some of their phenotypic characteristics were similar to *Xoo* while others were similar to *Xoor* (Table 2). In several characteristics, the T strains gave the same responses as the low-virulent *Xoo* strain X1-5 from Texas, USA (Table 2).

Genomic DNA of the T strains (T1, T2), a virulent *Xoo* strain from India (A3857), a low-virulent strain from the USA (X1-8), and *Xoor* strains (BLS292, BLS298, BLS303) were compared by Southern blot analysis. The four DNA probes used were the plasmids pJEL101

and pTnX1, which contain repetitive, mobile DNA elements; *pBSavrXa10*, which has a cloned avirulence gene from *Xoo*; and two *EcoRI* fragments (8.3 and 5.2 Kb, isolated from plasmid p23-44 and containing part of the *hrp* genes from *Xoo*).

The hybridization patterns of the T strains were clearly different from the patterns observed for the other strains. The pTnX1 probe did not hybridize with DNA from T1, T2, or X1-8. The cloned avirulence gene (*pBSavrXa10*) hybridized with DNA from T1 and T2, but with far fewer bands than those observed in the *Xoo* and *Xoor* strains. X1-8 did not hybridize with *pBSavrXa10*. Fewer bands of the T strains and X1-8 DNA hybridized with *hrp* genes and PJEL101 than were observed in the *Xoo* and *Xoor* strains; patterns for X1-8 and T1 and T2 clearly differed. Therefore, the genome organization of the T strains is clearly different from the Indian *Xoo* strain, the *Xoor* strains, and the USA strain (X1-8) from *Xoo*.

This study indicates that these two low-virulent bacterial strains associated with rice cannot be satisfactorily placed into current taxonomic groups using the available tests for phenotypic characteristics, molecular probes, and plant inoculations. Such strains might represent an evolutionary phase between BB and BLS pathogens of rice. Alternatively, they may belong to a completely different pathovar that has become associated with rice by chance. Although their importance is uncertain, the strains need to be monitored carefully for changes in their virulence to rice. ■

Reaction of promising rice cultivars to gall midge (GM) in coastal Karnataka, India

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GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) is the most important pest of rice in the coastal region of Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka State. We screened 55 promising cultures for resistance during 1990-92 wet seasons (WS).

Cultures were transplanted in 4-m rows spaced at 20 cm. We recorded number of tillers and silver shoots 50 d after transplanting for 10 randomly selected hills per row. Twenty entries were resistant (see table). ■

Reaction of promising rice cultivars to GM infestation in the field. Karnataka, India, 1990-92 WS.

Av percentage of tillers as shoots	Lines
0-5	IET9689, IET10260, IET10770, IET11162, IET10747, IET10775, IET12489, IET10765, IET10247, IET10867, IET10312, IET7428, IET9552, IET10418, IET11396, IET10765, Shakti, Phalguna, KKP6, KKP2
5-10	IET6461, IET11089, IET11122, IET11465, IET7830, IET7303, IET10751, IET10864, IET10668, IET3039, IET7956, MO 4, Cul 170, Cul 168, KMS83-1, GMR17
10-20	IET10333, IET11452, IET10735, IET10318, CTH1, MO 5, MO 6, MO 7, Cul 204, Cul 126, Cul 170, Cul 93, Cul 153-1, Cul 22332-2, Cul 200, Annapurna, Bharathi
20 or more	IET10748, Jaya (check)

Rice cultures resistant to rice gall midge (GM) biotypes 1 and 4 under artificial infestation in greenhouse

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At least four distinct GM biotypes exist in India. We have been rearing biotypes 1 and 4 (both prevalent in AP) under strict greenhouse isolation conditions. Biotype 1 (the original Hyderabad population) has been maintained on TN1 at DRR since 1976. Biotype 4 was built up from the endemic population of Srikakulam district, AP, and is maintained on Phalguna rice, which is resistant to biotype 1 and susceptible to biotype 4.

We evaluated 1,295 elite breeding lines from DRR-coordinated national yield and observational nurseries against the two biotypes. The standard screening

Advanced breeding lines of rice showing resistance to GM biotypes 1 and 4 in greenhouse, DDR, Hyderabad, AP, India, 1988-90.

Line	Designation	Cross	Source of resistance against	
			Biotype 1	Biotypes 1 and 4
IET10743 IET10742 IET11377	CR309 selections	Orumundakan/ CRM6-106		Orumundakan
IET11375	CR308-38	Orumundakan/ Damodar		Orumundakan
-	CR308-408	Orumundakan/ Damodar		Orumundakan
-	CR311-34	Orumundakan/ Dasal		Orumundakan
-	CR311-134	Orumundakan/ Dasal		Orumundakan
-	CRM24	Orumundakan mutant		Orumundakan
IET9709 IET9710 IET9711 IET9853 IET9854 IET10300 IET10746 IET10831 IET10849 IET11104	RP2068 selections	Swarnadhan/ Velluthacheera		Velluthacheera
-	R296 selections	CR157-392/ OR57-21		Ptb10
-	CR157-912	Vijaya/Ptb10		Ptb10
-	RP1528-1237-39	CR97-1550/ARC7328		Ptb21
IET11483	RTN14-1-1-1	IR36/CR57-MR1523		Ptb21
IET11384	RTN121-1-1-1-1	CR57-MR1523/IR36// RTN68		Ptb21
IET11385	RTN332-4-2-1	CR57-40/RTN711		Ptb21
IET11452	RTN29-1-1	CR57-MR1523/IR36		Ptb21
-	WGL 47805	BPT3301/CR57-MR1523		Ptb21
IET10744	CR386-23-5-4	ARC6650/CR94-721-3		Ptb18 Ptb21
IET10412	CR407-6-1	CR94/Ratna		Ptb21
IET12348	CR404-14-1	CR94-1512-6/Usa 2-21		Ptb21
-	RP2629-44-33-21	IET8682/IR60		Ptb21
IET10371	Pusa 510	IR36/Pusa 167		Ptb21
IET11164	R281-12	Poorva/IR8608-298		Ptb21
IET10885	TNAU842805	TNAU9426-6/IR50		Ptb21
IET12364	MTU6203	MTU4570/IR50		Ptb21
IET10247	OR633-7	Jajati/Ob677	Ob677	
IET11508	RP2543 selections	Rasi/RP1579-39	Siam 29	
IET11517 IET12873	RP2547-130-272	ARC5723/ARC6650// RP1579-38	Siam 29	
-	RP2547-100-255	RP1579-38	Siam 29	
-	RP2547-111-259	RP1579-38	Siam 29	
IET10451	OR487-30-3	T90/IR8/RPW6-13// Siam 29	Siam 29	
-	OR447-20-8	IR8/Siam 29// Parijat///Rasi	Siam 29	
IET11514	RP1959-56- 88-426-30-52	Swarnadhan/Phalguna	Siam 29	
-	RP2541-8642-357	Swarnadhan/RP1579-36	Siam 29	

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